

Knowledge Sharing and Organisational Agility of Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract—Organisation agility is crucial for success in today's fast-paced and rapidly changing business environment. Hence, this study investigate the influence of knowledge sharing on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design was adopted. Population consists of 589 administrative officers from all tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample size of the population is two hundred and thirty - four (234) administrative officers which was gotten with the use of Krejcie and Morgan Sampling Technique. The reliability coefficient ranges from 0.711. Data collected were analyzed using inferential statistics. Findings revealed that knowledge sharing was found to significantly influenced organizational agility ($Adj R^2 = 0.967$). The study concluded that knowledge sharing singly had significant influence on organizational agility. The study recommended that since knowledge sharing positively influence organizational agility, management of tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria should adopt official policies on knowledge sharing that align with organizational agility goals.

Keywords—Administrative Officers, Knowledge Sharing, organizational Agility

I. INTRODUCTION

Agility is the response to opportunity and threat within and outside an organisational environment which the result will be innovative performance. It is also the ability to shift direction in response to new information, opportunity or challenges in an organisation. To stay competitive and become more flexible, agility has been put on the agenda of many organisations aiming at achieving competitive edge in the society, better innovation performance, or higher team morale. Organisation agility is crucial for success in today's fast-paced and rapidly changing business environment (Felipe et al, 2020). It enables organisations to respond quickly to shifting market conditions, academic conditions, students/customers' needs and technological advancements. Agile organisations can innovate, adapt, and evolve rapidly, staying ahead of the competition and achieving sustained growth and profitability.

By embracing agility, organisations can foster a culture of experimentation, learning, and continuous improvement which allows them to identify and capitalize on new opportunities, mitigate risks and threats and navigate uncertainty (Felipe et al, 2020). Agile organisations are better equipped to handle disruptions pivot when necessary and stay relevant in ever changing landscape. Ultimately, organisational agility is essential for driving innovation, enhancing customers/students'

satisfaction, and achieving long – term success. It enables organisations to stay nimble, responsive, and competitive, ensuring they remain relevant and thrive in a rapidly evolving world. This particularly applies to organisations in developed countries which are always on hand to leverage digital technologies to enhance agility, change, innovation and response to potential threat in order to reposition their organisation to be able to absorb global threat and also take advantage of opportunities as they inherently face higher complexities due to the number of collaborating units, faculties and departments, which are themselves embedded in rigid hierarchies (Frankowska & Rzczycki, 2020). This agile preparedness among developed countries is lacking in Africa countries where infrastructural challenges is the bane of development which has hindered organisational agility.

In Nigeria for example, complex regulatory environment, inability of organisations to develop agile talent and leadership has negatively impacted organisation success except for few giant oil and gas firms in the south-south part of the country and some international organisations in other part of Nigeria (Gentsoudi, 2023). Nevertheless, tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria seem to be experiencing low level of agility among its staff. This could be due to several reasons such as spread of rigid hierarchical structures and slow decision-making processes among the leadership and management of the institutions, infrastructural decay and technological limitation in innovation and adaptation, cultural and attitudinal barriers to change among existing staff, lack of visionary leadership and ineffective management. The frequent change of policies and regulations to suite the government in power create uncertainty and hinder agility. This has led to tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria to struggle for academic and innovative change, inability to meet industry requirements and global standard in technological field. This increase in limited agility has hindered innovation, research and academic development, talented staff seek opportunities in more agile and dynamic environment in other tertiary institutions in and outside the country. Hence, diversity and agility of administrative officers of tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria is poor due to low level of information management implementation. Knowledge sharing is a process that helps organizations find, select, organize, and publish critical information. It enhances adaptability to change in an organisation.

Knowledge sharing is a specialty that is essential for activities such as problem solving, dynamic learning, strategic

planning and decision making (Muukkonen et. al., 2020). Global competition has increased the pressure on organizations to upgrade services and ultimately upgrade their information systems. Knowledge sharing is a strategic need for institutions and organizations and ensures long-term advantages for organizations and communities; it is the extent to which organizations and institutions benefit from human, intellectual and informational capital (Muukkonen et. al., 2020). The most important goal in applying knowledge sharing in the organization is to adapt quickly to changes in the surrounding environment to enhance efficiency and effectiveness. As a result, knowledge sharing refers to the process of how to create, disseminate and use knowledge in an organization.

Knowledge is an organizational asset that can be used to generate and develop new processes and best practices to respond and anticipate changes (Panda, 2021). It is also an essential source of intellectual capital, which helps organizations differentiate themselves from competitors and achieve higher competent and performance. Intellectual capital encompassing various organizational resources, through the investment of knowledge, information, innovation and technology, creativity and intellectual property, professional skills and know-how in achieving sustaining distinctive values and effective performance, is an important source of competitive advantage. Knowledge is the quality that empowers individuals and organisations to stay competitive in the borderless world of academics. Organisational dependence on resources to obtain greater output has moved from physical resources to knowledge and skills resources. Knowledge is not only information but a source of resource with asset value that can support organisations to function efficiently. Knowledge residing within individual employees plays a critical role in improvement of structural capability in form of organisational performance. Knowledge is regarded as a factor of production alongside land, labour, and capital and is considered as the most important resource in an organisation (Perdana, 2023).

One of the most crucial elements enabling knowledge acquisition in every academic institution is knowledge sharing infrastructure. Knowledge sharing refers to all the procedures that an organization does to create, choose, organize, utilize, and communicate knowledge as well as transfer significant data and experiences, the relationships that an administrative officer can adapt and apply will surely affect how well they grasp the data set (Rafi, 2022). There would not be knowledge sharing without the ability to handle knowledge, in its simplest form, knowledge is a body of information, this could imply that the knowledge is concealed behind theories, procedures, or systems or that it is expressed through opinions, theories, ideas, and analyses. Knowledge-oriented management seeks to extract knowledge from information and transform that knowledge into a long-lasting competitive advantage that can be used to gauge an organization's success. In order to achieve academic goals and strategies, management entails encouraging resources both human such as personnel, and artificial such as technologies to work together in a coordinated manner. With administrative officers realizing that a significant portion of their academic institution worth depends on its capacity to develop and manage knowledge, knowledge sharing has emerged as a key theme in many major institutions, for an organization to achieve greater organizational performance and gain a lasting competitive advantage.

Administrative officers must participate in effective knowledge sharing methods, the competitive environment of the local and international markets is accompanied by the growing requirement for effective knowledge sharing in all areas, whether inside or outside the organization. Hence, this study tends to investigate Information handling capability, organisational climate, knowledge sharing and organisational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nigeria and Africa, operate in a dynamic environment shaped by policy changes, technological advancements, and increasing stakeholder expectations. The ability of these institutions to remain responsive and adaptive demonstrating organisational agility is crucial for effective academic performance. However, administrative officers play a critical role in ensuring institutional adaptability, as they manage information systems, facilitate communication, and implement decisions. Their ability to share knowledge efficiently determines how agile an institution can be. However, many institutions exhibit weaknesses in these areas, limiting their ability to respond swiftly to emerging challenges. A clear example of this challenge was seen during the COVID-19 pandemic when many tertiary institutions in Nigeria including tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria struggled to transition to online learning. Unlike institutions with agile administrative systems, those with resistance to change and ineffective knowledge-sharing structures experienced prolonged academic disruptions.

By providing empirical insights, the research aims to enhance administrative efficiency, improve institutional responsiveness, and foster a culture of adaptability in higher education. Administrative officers of tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria are involved in knowledge sharing in the institutions. Preliminary investigation, close observation and literature review indicate that information and records do take time to be processed by the administrative officers, and this has made it difficult to retrieve the required information as and when due (Panda, 2021). It is however becoming clearer that this is common knowledge among tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria because accurate, reliable and trustworthy information that fulfil evidential requirements are being created but not properly managed. If care is not taken and the slide in information processing among administrative officers of the institutions is not checked, there would be delay in students' results, delay in posting graduating students for National Youth Service Corps and delay in transcript issuance, difficulties in quick response to research opportunities, and decrease in research productivity and program development, increased in time – to – degree and decreased graduation rates, decrease in enrolment and revenue as students seek out more responsive and innovative institutions. This will lead to difficulties and struggle in integration of new and advanced technologies leading to decreased in administrative effectiveness and efficiency. Despite the recognised importance of information handling capability, organisational climate, and knowledge sharing in fostering agility, there is limited empirical research This study, therefore, seeks to examine the impact of knowledge sharing on the organisational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is:

determine the influence of knowledge sharing on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria;

Hypothesis

The following were the research hypotheses that were tested:

H₀₁: There is significant influence of knowledge sharing on organizational agility of administrative officers of tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Figure 1 Conceptual Model Framework Illustrating the Influence of Knowledge Sharing on Organisational Agility of Administrative Officers of Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Source: Researcher's Conceptual Framework, 2026

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Organisational Agility

Agility emphasizes speed and flexibility as the primary attributes of an agile organization. An equally important attribute of agility is the effective response to change and uncertainty. Responding to change in proper ways and exploiting and taking advantages of changes are the main factors of agility (Mangalaraj et al., 2022). Agility refers to the proactive responses to changes. Agility refers to the use of changes as inherent opportunities in turbulent environment. Agility refers to the ability to survive and progress in the variable and unpredictable environment. Organizational flexibility represents an organization's capacity to adjust its internal structures and processes in a predetermined response to changes in the environment. Adaptability underlies the fit of organizational operations to their environment while flexibility emphasizes the readiness of organizational resources and the ease of resource mobilization. The "agility" concept encompasses both flexibility and adaptability. Agility, as a business concept, was coined in a manufacturing context-particularly in relation to flexible manufacturing systems¹⁷. Agility is a new concept in contemporary administrative thought. One writer has defined the process of agility in terms of the capabilities necessary to achieve light movement in the organization (Manurung, 2022).

Agility is the ability to respond to unpredictable changes with quick response and profitability. Agility is an organizational ability to react quickly and effectively to an environment which can change radically. The concept of agility means rapid, agile, and active movement. Also, agility refers to the ability of rapid and easy movement and rapidly thinking with a thoughtful method. The root or origin of agility is derived from agile production, and this is a concept that has been presented during later years. The agile production has been accepted as a successful strategy by producers that prepare them for a considerable performance. According to the different definitions of the word

agility, the concept of speed, quick response and also the concepts of group work and common goal regarding the word organization can be inferred. Agility can be defined as swiftness and quick response of a harmonious group to the changes made by the environment surrounding them in order to reach a goal (Manurung, 2022).

Organisational agility is the organization's ability to respond quickly and effectively to unexpected opportunities, in addition to providing, in advance, solutions that meet potential needs. Organisation agility is the ability to survive and grow in an unexpected competitive environment of constant change through rapid response to changing environment and through meeting the desires and needs of academic environment of services (Mulyono & Syamsuri, 2023). Organisation agility is the successful application of the competition rules, such as speed, flexibility, innovation and quality, through the means of integration of resources and the restructuring of best practices in the environment of technical knowledge, through the provision of services or products that meet academics' preferences in light of a rapidly changing environment. Organisational agility is the organization's ability to work comfortably in a quickly and consistently changing and fragmented global environment, through producing high quality and effective performance.

Organisational agility enables the organization to carry out a series of specific tasks successfully, in addition to managing the opportunities and risks in the administrative activities effectively (Pereira, 2021). Organisational agility makes organizations more responsive to innovative trends, and faster in terms of the delivery of services compared to non-agile ones. Organisational agility is composed of three basic dimensions of the sensor agility, decision-making, and agility practice and application. Organisational agility is not only "flexible" to cater for predictable changes but also is able to respond and adapt to unpredictable changes quickly and efficiently. Organisational agility can be viewed as the state of organizational performance in terms of flexibility and adaptability and is attainable through organization's activities. In particular, from the process-based perspective, organisational agility is a set of processes that allow an organization to sense changes and respond efficiently and effectively in timely and cost-effective manner in the internal and external environments. Sensing refers to an organization's ability to detect, capture and interpret organizational opportunities. Responding represents an organizational ability to mobilize and transform resources to react to the opportunities that it senses. These two capabilities must be aligned to optimally obtain organisational agility. Organisational agility is the organizational capacity to sensor response successfully to the opportunities and threats in the market in a timely manner. Organisational agility is a proactive management strategy that aims at maintaining the organization's resources and achieving the desires of students in a timely manner.

The concept of organisational agility is derived from performance characteristics of an agile organization and is rooted in two related concepts- "organizational adaptability" and "organizational flexibility". Organizational adaptability focuses on how an organization's form, structure, and degree of formalization influence its ability to quickly adapt to its

environment. Organisational agility consists of several key elements. They are; speed and flexibility, responding to changes in the surrounding environment, high quality products, products and services of accurate information, interacting with social issues and the environment, different technologies collecting, and internal integration inside the institutions and among each other (Rafi, 2022). Organisational agility is the process of arrangement, and abolition of business units, markets and industries to re-focus on differentiated core capabilities. Organisational agility is a package of ideas that aims at continuous improvement, flat organizational structures, and work teams, stopping waste or loss, efficient use of resources, and managing the chain of preparation.

B. Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge has been defined as broad and abstract. A general definition of knowledge is “justified true belief”, “truthfulness and justification” of knowledge and combined with ideas, rules, procedures and information (Selivanovskikh, et. al., 2020). Some authors considered knowledge, information and data to be separate notions. The knowledge creation concept involves transforming data to information and then to knowledge. Raw data is a nucleus part of information that can be shaped and formed to create information. Information is data systematically organized into a useful form that is readily shared and accessed. But information and data are not meaningful until applied to a specific purpose and context. During the information process, knowledge is created through human intervention and interpretation in a given situation. Thus, the essential aspects of knowledge relate to human actions through language or demonstration.

Knowledge is the availability and formation of expertise, information, and competencies that shape new capabilities, result in better performance, motivate innovation, and generate higher value for administrative officers (Soto-Acosta & Wensley, 2015). Visionary administrative officers always consider and focus on the need of developing and utilizing knowledge for the prosperity of the organization. Knowledge can be described as understanding the association, situation, phenomena, concepts, and procedures of a prevailing problem or domain. With respect to the competitive advantage, knowledge has vital and increasing significance in organizations. Knowledge of the contemporary situation is regarded as the foundation of innovations in organizations. Hence, organizations are intensely required to recognize innovative knowledge for innovation initiation. Knowledge is broadly categorized into two kinds that are explicit and tacit knowledge. The explicit form of knowledge is found in textbooks, research articles, and guiding manuals; however, tacit knowledge is difficult to contextualize. Defining tacit knowledge said, “What are unsaid and unexpressed could be the reservoirs of tacit knowledge”. So, it is difficult to acquire, identify, and communicate tacit knowledge for an organization. Knowledge sharing meant gathering information and communicating to the individuals in demand. Collective activities that favorably enhance the resource of organizational knowledge, including gaining, formation, application, and communication of knowledge, are called knowledge sharing.

It is essential for organizations to have the ability of recognizing and leveraging new knowledge for competing in the market and attaining competitiveness. Thus, an important concern of the

organizations arises is how they can effectively allocate resources while developing new products and services that create a competitive edge for the organizations over their rivals. For this reason, an organisation is required to incorporate knowledge in the way of value creation from the intangible resources of an organization. Sharing of knowledge comprises of various elements, including identifying, recognizing, generating, applying, communicating, and storing it. Activities of knowledge sharing are decisive for innovation application (Swanson, et. al., 2020). Consequently, the organizational role is not merely limited to the acquisition of competences. Moreover, organizations are essentially required to develop organizational knowledge as it is regarded as a resource and a foundation of competitiveness and differentiation in the organization.

Irrespective of the knowledge generation or innovation, the knowledge wave started was when people involved in sharing knowledge among groups or persons. Many organizations recognized creativity as the key to competitive advantages, and knowledge is the key to continuous creativity (Cegarra-Navarro, et. al., 2016). Creative knowledge has become a topic of wider attention in research. Based on the extensive literature, this research considers gaining, creation, storage, and diffusion of knowledge as the primary constructs of knowledge sharing capabilities. The first kind of capabilities deals with the structure of knowledge sharing because it provides a framework to the organization that enables the knowledge flow within the organization, as well as in the external context. These kinds of capabilities are called “knowledge infrastructure capabilities”. The second kind of capabilities are associated with the dynamic activities of knowledge sharing by recognizing dynamic variations in the environment and making the organization able to adopt capabilities that may effectively deal with these dynamic changes. These kinds of capabilities are called “knowledge-based dynamic capabilities”.

C. Knowledge Sharing and Organisational Agility

A scholar set out to study the impact of knowledge management systems, organizational climate, and attitude on the intention of employees to share knowledge (Ekweli & Hamilton, 2020). Their findings showed that attitude was the most significant factor but that knowledge management systems self-efficacy, and organizational climate, by positively contributing to attitude, indirectly affected knowledge sharing. A researcher assessed the antecedents of organizational knowledge sharing, including the intentions and attitude of the knowledge sharer, rewards for knowledge sharing, and the organizational culture. Their findings provided support for a positive relationship between all three areas studied and KSB; furthermore, their findings suggested it is easier to motivate employees to share knowledge in collectivist cultures than in individualist ones. From a different perspective, findings suggest that knowledge hiding, as opposed to knowledge sharing, also affects group performance, but in the opposite manner. Groups in which the members are prone to hoarding behaviour when it comes to knowledge tend to perform at a lower level.

A scholar perused the relationship between the process of knowledge sharing and organizational agility among personnel of Agriculture- Jahad Organization in Share-Kord (Rafi, 2022).

Research population included 150 experts at Jihad - Keshavarzi in Shahre- Kord, that 150 of them were selected as research sample. Results confirmed that there is a positive relationship between organizational agility and process of knowledge sharing. Also this study indicated a positive relationship between adaptable organization design and process of knowledge sharing and leadership and identity and process of knowledge sharing, that their amount respectively equal to 50% and 56%. Organizational culture affects knowledge sharing and job satisfaction greatly, and knowledge sharing plays an important mediatory role between organizational culture and job satisfaction.

A scholar observed that knowledge management improves organizational learning (Ly,2023). Similarly, a scholar examined knowledge management practices through IT, and organisational performance in Slovenia and Croatia. The study reported that knowledge management heavily relies on technology, and requires trust and other supportive organisations elements. Also, a researcher examined the relationship between organizational culture and knowledge management. The study's results showed a statistically significant correlation between different types of organizational culture and knowledge management processes; while a scholar examined the relationship between knowledge management and academic performance in Iraq using correlation and regression analysis and found that that KM tools are useful for quality of education. Similarly, in an examination on knowledge management in relation to education in Malaysia, and found a significant difference in knowledge management processes with respect to public and private Universities in Malaysia. In addition, a researcher assessed knowledge management practices and performance of Nigerian Universities. The study found that variations in knowledge management practices result to differences in organisational performance. In the same vein, a scholar examined the impact of knowledge management and organisational performance of selected commercial banks in Nigeria, and found that knowledge acquisition has a positive effect on organisational performance.

V. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. *Dynamic Capabilities Theory of Agility*

The Dynamic capability theory (DCT) views agility as an organizations ability to as an organizations ability to purposefully adopt, integrate and reconfigure internal and external resources to respond to rapidly changing environment, when applied to agility, indicators are usually grouped into sensing, seizing and reconfiguring capabilities. It was also stated that agility is emerging as 'an important dynamic capability in contemporary academic environments (Roberts & Grover, 2021). Dynamic Capabilities is an organisation's potential to systematically solve problems, formed by its propensity to sense opportunities and threats, to make timely and market oriented decisions, and to change it resource base. Specifically agility drivers (sensing change) and agility capabilities (speed, responsiveness, competency, and flexibility) are similar to this definition in terms of its dynamic nature. In a thorough summary of the research conducted in the area of Dynamic Capabilities. Research

conducted between has been around characteristics of Dynamic Capabilities, while more recent research has focused on Dynamic Capabilities and performance outcomes.

In today's highly competitive business environment, agility is crucial for all organizations. Three main reasons for change agility are to more agile organisations are faster and more effectively can adapt; enabled to advance in making strategic moves at a faster pace than their competitors and be a competitive advantage. The following dimensions and measurements of organisation agility were extracted from the theory; sensing agility: In recent years, organizations have emphasized more strategic agility due to the dynamic and rapidly changing business environment. Sensing agility is the ability of an organisation to detect changes through the opportunities and threats existing in an academic environment to respond quickly by reorganizing its resources, procedures, and strategies. Sensing agility is a process whereby an organization speedily and effectively adapts its plans in response to unforeseen changes, interruptions and emerging market opportunities. Sensing agility is one of the main dimensions of organizational change agility which was measured using four components: strategic vision, policy and policymaking, missions, and values. A thorough review of the literature on strategic agility demonstrates that among the elements of Sensing agility are information technology capacity, human resource capability, competence, adaptability, flexibility, speed, strategic insight, responsiveness, internal response orientation, and external response orientation.

Seizing capacity is about an organization's capability to adapt efficiently and effectively in response to changes in the market. Seizing capacity is the ability to quickly change operation activities from manufacturing to supplying goods or services in a manner that has no significant penalty on time, cost, quality, and functionality. An organization can flex and adapt its operations, technology, and information to constantly evolving academic requirements brought on by market dynamics, competitive pressure, and business turbulence. Sensing operational changes which are mentioned as the physical ability to act, and capabilities for responding to operational changes mentioned as the intellectual ability to find the appropriate courses of action as factors of operational agility. Innovation to future trends, financial impact, non-financial impact, human resource agility, non-human resource agility, agile stakeholders' perception, and management were identified as indicators of operation agility

Transforming capacity is the ability to deal with change and handle and adapt to change when it arises. It plays a pivotal role in fostering change agility in an organization. Transforming capacity for change is a multidimensional comprising different aspects of leadership, culture, employee behavior, and an organizational infrastructure supporting organizational change. Transforming capacity for change has been an emerging area of research interest over the past decade. The author also mentioned that structural flexibility, encouraging participation in change processes, communication, learning, transformational leadership, and organization culture as elements of capacity for change (Roberts & Grover, 2021). Main components of transforming capacity are human skill sets, resources, formal systems and procedures, organizational culture, values, and norms. Similarly, structural flexibility, culture, technology, trustworthy leadership, transformational leadership, communication, support for change,

and learning were identified as determinants of transforming capacity for change.

B. SECI Model

The SECI Model has become the vital element of knowledge creation and transfer (Sveiby, Karl – Erik, 2021). They proposed four ways in which explicit and tacit knowledge can be created, combined, converted and shared in an organisation. The acronym of the SECI stand for Socialisation, Externalisation, Combination and Internalisation and are phases that occur when tacit and explicit knowledge interact. Socialisation involves sharing knowledge in face-face interaction; Externalisation happens when tacit is converted into implicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge is what people carry in their minds and we find it difficult to access. Explicit knowledge on the other hand, is what is documented or codified and can be transferred easily to others. Combination involves tacit knowledge transferred into explicit knowledge and explicit knowledge to explicit knowledge is Internalization. The cycle then continues. This section explores the mechanisms of knowledge sharing within by administrative officers of academic institutions using the SECI model.

During the knowledge conversion process where knowledge is captured and converted into useful documented and stored data, the SECI model is a relevant model (Sveiby, Karl – Erik, 2021). The Socialisation phase happens when knowledge that is exchanged is received through face-to-face interactions. This knowledge is tacit in nature, meaning that tacit knowledge is intuitive in nature and hard to define. It is majorly experience-based knowledge. Tacit knowledge being experience-based holds a great deal of value and enhances growth of any organisation. Socialisation can happen in a tertiary institution to aid in knowledge sharing i.e. during seminar classes where lecturers using experiences gained to transfer knowledge to students in the form of new ideas, inspiration and debates or when an administrative officer transfer knowledge from the management to the entire academic community or among themselves. Moreover, administrators of the tertiary institutions deliver the mission and vision of the academic institution during meetings, workshops where they delve deeper into what is required of every individual to the betterment of the institution. Employees are, thus, given a chance to share ideas with the superiors of the institution, leading to innovation and competitiveness as well as knowledge being shared.

The Externalisation phase of knowledge conversion happens when knowledge captured is changed into codified knowledge. This knowledge can be documented and therefore easy to store, identify and retrieve. This type of knowledge is called explicit knowledge. During Externalisation, tacit knowledge is changed into explicit knowledge. This means that the all the experiences, and intuitive knowledge are documented and stored into accessible storage areas such as documents, databases, manuals, etc. this is done so as to spread knowledge efficiently and effectively throughout the institution. Here Management aids in this process by encouraging partners, administrative officers to document academic records so as to make available when needed which will add value to the institution but also share knowledge as well. ICT systems/applications would be beneficial to the institution such as computer systems for retrieving such information and knowledge, databases for storage of the

knowledge. This not only aids students to access their records but also, access knowledge from other academics, thus achieving a knowledge sharing culture.

Furthermore, the third phase of the SECI model, the Combination phase, is a combination of the explicit knowledge (Sveiby, Karl – Erik, 2021). New knowledge is created when explicit knowledge is combined to form new ideas thus innovation. For instance, reviewing of relevant literature related to a certain study, for example, community psychology can lead to new knowledge exchanged and received. By combining different scholarly works and distributing them among students during lecture sessions and creating debate sessions, students are able to participate in knowledge sharing activities with the lecturers' encouragement. In addition, during department meetings held by the university, when colleagues get together, they can combine the knowledge they have to create better teaching modules, improve their personal reputation and also improve team cohesiveness among departments. In addition to the module creation, knowledgeable ideas received from industry practitioners allows departmental heads to use these ideas to innovate new lecture notes and offer direction to students.

The final stage of the SECI spiral model is the internalisation phase of knowledge conversion which happens when codified knowledge is internalised within oneself. For example, when students take part in discussion forums either in groups or during coursework assignments and also on discussion platforms on virtual learning environments (e.g. Moodle, Blackboard), this helps students to internalise the knowledge they have gained based on their understanding and allowing them to modify it. The more they indulge in discussion forums while interacting either on IT platforms or face-to-face, the more knowledge is shared amongst the students. The same applies to academics. With the use of Nonaka and Takeuchi model of knowledge conversion, the SECI model, as discussed, at least all factors are taken into consideration to encourage knowledge sharing within academia and administrative setting.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross sectional survey research design was used. The purpose of the design is to address the state of affairs as it exists. It can be used when collecting information about people's attitudes, opinions, habits or any of the variety of education or social issues. The cross sectional survey research design was used to describe events in relation to Knowledge Sharing and Organisational Agility of Administrative Officers in Tertiary Institutions in Oyo State, Nigeria. The population of this study consists of all the five hundred and eighty – nine (589) Administrative Officers of Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample size is two hundred and thirty-nine which was gotten from Krejcie and Morgan Sampling Technique in Table 1 below. The data collected for the study were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 31. The hypothesis in the study was tested at level of 0.05 significance.

Table 1: Table for determining sample size of a known population

N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S
10	0	100	80	280	162	800	260	2800	338
15	14	110	86	290	165	850	265	3000	341
20	19	120	92	300	169	900	269	3500	346
25	24	130	97	320	175	950	274	4000	351
30	28	140	103	340	181	1000	278	4500	354
35	32	150	108	360	186	1100	285	5000	357
40	36	160	113	380	191	1200	291	6000	302
45	40	170	118	400	196	1300	297	7000	364
50	44	180	123	420	201	1400	302	8000	367
55	48	190	127	440	205	1500	306	9000	368
60	52	200	132	460	210	1600	310	10000	370
65	56	210	136	480	214	1700	313	15000	375
70	59	220	140	500	217	1800	317	20000	377
75	63	230	144	550	226	1900	320	30000	379
80	66	240	148	600	234	2000	322	40000	380
85	70	250	152	650	242	2200	327	50000	381
90	73	260	155	700	248	2400	331	75000	382
95	76	270	159	750	254	2600	335	100000	384

Source: Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Sample Size Determination Table

Result of Test of Hypothesis

There is no significance influence of knowledge sharing on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 2: Summary of Regression Analysis of influence of knowledge sharing on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 2a: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.983 ^a	.967	.967	1.78120

A Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge Sharing

Table 2b: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	25206.129	1	25206.129	7944.801	.000 ^b
	Residual	859.790	272	3.173		
	Total	26065.919	273			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Agility

b. Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge Sharing

Table 2c: Coefficients^b

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	5.602		.534	.983
	Knowledge Sharing	1.457		.016	89.134

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Agility

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 2a revealed the result of model summary where knowledge sharing has strong positive and statistically significant influence on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria ($R = 0.983$, $p < 0.05$). The coefficient of determination (Adj. R^2) of 0.967 shows that knowledge sharing 96.7% of the changes in knowledge sharing of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria, while the remaining 3.3% changes in knowledge sharing of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria is attributable to other external factors other than those examined in this study. From the Table 2b the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test revealed that knowledge sharing has a significant influence on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. This can be explained by the F-value (7944.801) and low p-value (0.000) which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Hence, the result posited that knowledge sharing found in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria significantly influenced organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Furthermore, the results of regression coefficients in table 2c revealed that a positive and statistically significant relative influence was reported for all the knowledge sharing considered. Specifically, the results reveal that at 95% confidence level, knowledge sharing, ($\beta = 1.457$, $p = 0.000$, $t = 10.494$) of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria were statistically significant as the p-values were less than 0.05

and the t-values greater than 1.96. Also, the results of regression coefficients in Table 2c, posit that at 95% confidence level, a unit change in knowledge sharing will lead to a 1.457 increase in the organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria, given that all other factors are held constant. It is important to stress that all the measures of knowledge sharing had positive and significant relative influence on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. This study rejects the null hypothesis which states that knowledge sharing will have no significant influence on the organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

VII. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The hypothesis of the study was: there will be no significance influence of knowledge sharing on organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The null hypothesis was rejected as it was revealed that knowledge sharing significantly influenced organizational agility among administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. This agrees with the results of previous literature. A scholar set out to study the impact of knowledge management systems, organizational climate, and attitude on the intention of employees to share knowledge (Ekweli & Hamilton, 2020). Their findings showed that attitude was the most significant factor but that knowledge management systems self-efficacy, and organizational climate, by positively contributing to attitude, indirectly affected knowledge sharing. A researcher assessed the antecedents of organizational knowledge sharing, including the intentions and attitude of the knowledge sharer, rewards for knowledge sharing, and the organizational culture. Their findings provided support for a positive relationship between all three areas studied and KSB; furthermore, their findings suggested it is easier to motivate employees to share knowledge in collectivist cultures than in individualist ones. From a different perspective, findings suggest that knowledge hiding, as opposed to knowledge sharing, also affects group performance, but in the opposite manner. Groups in which the members are prone to hoarding behaviour when it comes to knowledge tend to perform at a lower level.

A scholar perused the relationship between the process of knowledge sharing and organizational agility among personnel of Agriculture- Jihad Organization in Share-Kord (Rafi, 2022). Research population included 150 experts at Jihad - Keshavarzi in Shahre- Kord, that 150 of them were selected as research sample. Results confirmed that there is a positive relationship between organizational agility and process of knowledge sharing. Also this study indicated a positive relationship between adaptable organization design and process of knowledge sharing and leadership and identity and process of knowledge sharing, that their amount respectively equal to 50% and 56%. Organizational culture affects knowledge sharing and job satisfaction greatly, and knowledge sharing plays an important mediatory role between organizational culture and job satisfaction.

A scholar observed that knowledge management improves organizational learning (Ly,2023). Similarly, a scholar examined

knowledge management practices through IT, and organisational performance in Slovenia and Croatia. The study reported that knowledge management heavily relies on technology, and requires trust and other supportive organisations elements. Also, a researcher examined the relationship between organizational culture and knowledge management. The study's results showed a statistically significant correlation between different types of organizational culture and knowledge management processes; while a scholar examined the relationship between knowledge management and academic performance in Iraq using correlation and regression analysis and found that that KM tools are useful for quality of education. Similarly, in an examination on knowledge management in relation to education in Malaysia, and found a significant difference in knowledge management processes with respect to public and private Universities in Malaysia. In addition, a researcher assessed knowledge management practices and performance of Nigerian Universities. The study found that variations in knowledge management practices result to differences in organisational performance. In the same vein, a scholar examined the impact of knowledge management and organisational performance of selected commercial banks in Nigeria, and found that knowledge acquisition has a positive effect on organisational performance.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study investigated knowledge sharing, and organizational agility of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The components of knowledge sharing (Socialisation, Externalization, Combination and Internalization), and organizational agility (Sensing Capability, Seizing Capability and Transforming Capability) of administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria were used to determine their effects of the components of knowledge sharing, and organizational agility through the administration of questionnaire. The results revealed that information handling capability, organizational climate, knowledge sharing had significant influence on organizational agility; Based on the empirical findings, this study concluded that there was a statistically significant influence of knowledge sharing on organizational agility among administrative officers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Also, the findings of this study strongly reinforce Dynamic Capability Theory of agility, which posits that organizations achieve sustained effectiveness through their ability to sense, seize, and reconfigure resources in response to environmental changes. Theoretically, this affirms the SECI model's relevance in public-sector and educational contexts and extends its explanatory power to agility-related outcomes rather than innovation alone.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations of this study are based on the findings of the study, especially as it relates to the outcome of the hypotheses tested.

1. Management should implement formal mechanisms such as knowledge repositories, communities of practice, and regular inter-departmental meetings to promote sharing of best administrative practices.

2. Since knowledge sharing positive influence organizational agility, management of tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria should adopt official policies on information handling, data security, and knowledge sharing that align with organizational agility goals.

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